

D4.1: Application ontology

<i>Authors (institution)</i>	Sridevi Krishnamurthi (SINTEF), Simon Clark (SINTEF)
<i>Deliverable type</i>	Other
<i>Dissemination level</i>	Public
<i>Submission date</i>	30 May 2024

SUMMARY SHEET

<i>Project Acronym</i>	BATMACHINE
<i>Project Title</i>	Boosting Europe's sustainable battery cell industrial manufacturing value chain by developing an optimised machinery with intelligent control processes to minimise costs, scrap and energy consumption
<i>Grant Agreement no.</i>	101104246
<i>Project Coordinator</i>	Kamil Burak Dermenci kamil.burak.dermenci@vub.be Aitor Sánchez aitor.sanchez@vub.be
<i>Project Duration</i>	VUB 1 st June 2023 – 30 th November 2026 (42 months)
<i>Deliverable No.</i>	D4.1
<i>Dissemination level*</i>	Public
<i>Lead beneficiary</i>	SINTEF
<i>Submission date</i>	30 May 2024
<i>Abstract</i>	<p>This deliverable is a demonstrator that provides application ontologies (in the form of .ttl files) for managing data derived from battery manufacturing equipment. Application ontologies have been created for describing resources from the following equipment suppliers: FOM, SKZ, NETZSCH, TEKNIKER and POMECA datasets.</p> <p>The application ontologies are structured such that each manufacturer has control over their own domain, with options for distinguishing public and private dissemination levels. This is achieved by hosting the source code for public and private terms in separate repositories under the BATMACHINE project on GitHub.com. Furthermore, Persistent Uniform Resource Locators (PURLs) have been established for each supplier through w3id.org that will allow the suppliers to retain control over their ontology resources after the end of the project.</p>

DISCLAIMER

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Project Overview

The BATMACHINE project is centred on strengthening Europe's battery cell industrial manufacturing value chain by developing new battery cell manufacturing machinery. This will be done while giving priority to minimising the energy for cell production, enhancing plant efficiency rates, and integrating intelligent control processes to reduce scrap.

The project will develop and implement an optimised and energy-efficient process chain considering:

- Slurry mixing (automated modular process set-up including monitoring techniques).
- Exclusive slot-die coating and drying novel machinery (with one side coating, a coating speed of 1 m/min up to 20 m/min and a web-width of 300 mm).
- A calendaring tool to be integrated in a battery manufacturer for process optimisation.

Moreover, intelligent control processes and Industry 4.0 will be intensively integrated through the creation of a collaborative and FAIR data space for battery production. Digital interfaces between battery manufacturing equipment, control system, and engineers will be developed with the aim of building universal digitalisation tools to enhance the battery production and create a battery passport. The environmental and economic impact of different machinery, production line configurations and factory designs will be deeply studied to reduce the cost and energy consumption of manufacturing processes.

List of Participants

1		VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	VUB	Belgium
2		FUNDACION TEKNIKER	TEKNIKER	Spain
3		SKZ-KFE GGMBH	SKZ	Germany
4		FOM TECHNOLOGIES A/S	FOM	Denmark
5		DEEP BLUE SRL	DBL	Italy
6		NETZSCH FEINMAHLTECHNIK GMBH	NFT	Germany
7		RHEINISCH-WESTFAELISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE AACHEN	RWTH AACHEN	Germany
8		SINTEF AS	SINTEF	Norway
8a		SINTEF OCEAN AS	SINTEF- OCEAN	Norway
9		POMEGA ENERJİ DEPOLAMA TEKNOLOJİLERİ ANONİM ŞİRKETİ	POMEGA	Turkey
10		CEGASA ENERGIA S.L.U.	CEGASA	Spain
11		LECLANCHÉ GMBH	LEC	Germany

Document Change Log

Version number	Date	Organization name	Description
0.1	10/05/2024	SINTEF	First draft
0.2	30/05/2024	SINTEF	Revised draft
0.3	30/05/2024	VUB	Final version

Partners' Contributions

Partner institution	Sections	Description of the contribution
SINTEF	All	Deliverable preparation
TEKNIKER, SKZ	All	Internal review

ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	Extended
CMS	Content management system
DMS	Document management system
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IRI	International Resource Identifier
KPI	Key Performance Index
PURL	Persistent Uniform Resource Locator
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SMTP	Simple Mail Transfer Protocol
WPL	Work Package Leader
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

The deliverable consists of application ontology files (.ttl files) developed for battery equipment manufacturers within the project, the ontology mappings are built on top of battery domain ontology which in turn are derived from the Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology (EMMO). These ontological frameworks provide a standardized approach to organizing and integrating data, fostering interoperability, and enabling advanced analytics.

Application ontologies have been created for describing resources from the following equipment suppliers: FOM, SKZ, NETZSCH, POMECA and TEKNIKER.

The application ontologies are structured such that each manufacturer has control over their own domain, with options for distinguishing public and private dissemination levels. This is achieved by hosting the source code for public and private terms in separate repositories under the BATMACHINE project on GitHub.com. Furthermore, the .ttl files contain unique persistent identifiers in the form of w3ids, these Persistent Uniform Resource Locators (PURLs) have been established for each supplier through will allow the suppliers to retain control over their ontology resources after the end of the project.

SINTEF Industry is responsible for creating and publishing the ontologies, with content input from the relevant partners.

1. Introduction

This deliverable provides application ontologies (.ttl files) specifically designed for managing data originating from battery manufacturing equipment. The core objective of these ontologies is to facilitate structured and semantic data management techniques, particularly focusing on the diverse data sets derived from measurements and machinery.

The application ontologies cover resources from major suppliers in the battery manufacturing sector, including FOM, SKZ, and NETZSCH. .

The work was extended beyond the initial scope to cover as well TEKNIKER and POMECA datasets. Each ontology is structured to ensure that suppliers maintain control over their respective domains, with options for distinguishing between public and private dissemination levels. This segregation is achieved through separate repositories under the BATMACHINE organization, with Persistent Uniform Resource Locators (PURLs) established for each supplier via w3id.org for long-term resource control.

Led by SINTEF Industry, this initiative involves collaboration from various stakeholders, with content contributions from relevant partners. Through the adoption of application ontologies, battery manufacturing equipment suppliers can effectively manage data complexities, extract actionable insights, and drive operational improvements in their respective domains. This introduction sets the stage for an in-depth exploration of how these ontologies empower structured and semantic data management practices within the battery manufacturing industry.

2. Objectives

The main objective of this work was to set up usable ontologies based on existing data from the partners. The versions of the ontologies are not considered final for two main reasons: consensual definitions will require iterations, and additional variables will become available as the equipment is developed.

Therefore, the main focus at this stage is that the infrastructure adheres to W3C / EMMO / FAIR best practices for publishing ontologies (e. g. PURL namespace, resolvable IRIs, RDF support, use of a top-level ontology framework, etc.).

On the scope of the ontologies, the priorities are (i) encoding the information that the partners have shared / asked for and (ii) make them available to ensure early testing of dataspaces deployment kit.

3. Application ontologies

The deliverable comprises application ontology files (.ttl) with supporting documentation for the relevant suppliers. This includes options for two dissemination

levels: public and private. This distinction is made to account for the potential need to restrict access to some non-public terms to a smaller group of users or developers. This report describes the public resources. Table 1 provides an overview of the public application ontologies created for this demonstrator, with links to the public source code repositories and documentation.

The .ttl files can be opened using Protégé, an ontology editor; the instructions to set it up can be found [here](#).

Table 1. Overview of the application ontologies that are covered by this demonstrator

Organization	Public Source Code Repository	Documentation
FOM	https://github.com/HEU-BATMACHINE/fom-public-resources	https://heu-batmachine.github.io/fom-public-resources/index.html
SKZ	https://github.com/HEU-BATMACHINE/skz-public-resources	https://heu-batmachine.github.io/skz-public-resources/index.html
TEKNIKER	https://github.com/HEU-BATMACHINE/tekniker-public-resources	https://heu-batmachine.github.io/tekniker-public-resources/index.html
NETZSCH	https://github.com/HEU-BATMACHINE/netzsch-public-resources	https://heu-batmachine.github.io/netzsch-public-resources/index.html
POMEGA	https://github.com/HEU-BATMACHINE/pomega-public-resources	https://heu-batmachine.github.io/pomega-public-resources/index.html
LEC	https://github.com/HEU-BATMACHINE/lec-public-resources	https://heu-batmachine.github.io/lec-public-resources/index.html

2.1 Development methodology

The content of the application ontologies is defined in cooperation with the relevant machine suppliers. This process begins with discussions among the suppliers and relevant stakeholders about the purpose and scope of the ontology. In this case, it was agreed that the ontologies would first focus on describing machine data from the various processes with the goal of establishing interoperability. Suppliers then provided the ontology developers with examples of typical datasets and files (.csvs, .tsvs & .xlsx file formats), which were used as a basis for creating terms and elucidations.

The application ontologies are connected to the top-level Elementary Multi-Perspective Materials Ontology (EMMO), which enables the applications to integrate with a much larger universe of relevant content, including battery and manufacturing domains.

Terms contained in the application ontologies are then mapped to relevant terms in EMMO (or other domains) to facilitate re-use and supplement the semantic descriptions. With the terms defined and mapped, the next step is to distinguish between public and private dissemination levels. Public terms are those that suppliers share with general public, while private terms are those that companies use for their own development purposes or are otherwise confidential. To achieve this distinction, the source code for public and private terms are hosted in separate repositories to avoid cross-contamination.

Figure 1. The Application ontologies inherit concepts from domain level ontology: electrochemistry and prefixed units which in turn inherits classes and properties from EMMO

The screenshot shows a GitHub repository page for 'tekniker-public-resources'. The repository is public and has 24 commits. The commit history table is as follows:

Commit	Message	Time
f602f03	Update context.json file	16 hours ago
	Update doc.yml	3 days ago
	update inferred version and namespace	17 hours ago
	Update context.json file	16 hours ago
	Update index.rst	18 hours ago
	Update README.md	16 hours ago
	ontology review	3 days ago
	update inferred version and namespace	17 hours ago
	update inferred version and namespace	17 hours ago

The README file is titled 'TEKNIKER Public Resources' and contains the following text:

This repository contains the source code for an ontology focused on describing the data generated by machinery used in battery manufacturing processes, developed by TEKNIKER. The ontology is defined under the top-level EMMO (Elementary Multiperspective Materials Ontology).

Overview

The TEKNIKER Battery Manufacturing Machinery Data Ontology provides a structured representation of the data produced by machinery used in battery manufacturing processes. It aims to standardize terminology, enhance data interoperability, and facilitate semantic reasoning over machinery-generated data.

Usage

Researchers, engineers, and stakeholders involved in battery manufacturing processes can use this ontology to:

- Standardize terminology for machinery-generated data
- Integrate heterogeneous data sources
- Enable semantic search and reasoning over machinery-generated data
- Facilitate the development of data-driven analytics and decision support systems

At the bottom of the page, there is a footer with the text: © 2024 GitHub, Inc. Terms Privacy Security Status Docs Contact Manage cookies Do not share my personal information

Figure 2. A screenshot of the GitHub repository created for hosting the ontologies.

A w3id.org PURL service is setup for each of the application ontologies to ensure that the IRIs are persistent and robust over the whole lifetime of the ontology. Separate PURL services are provided for each supplier to ensure that the organization retains full control over its terms and policies even after the project ends.

Finally, documentation for the public application ontologies is generated automatically from the .ttl files using sphinx and hosted on github pages. The PURLs are set to re-direct to the documentation, such that the IRIs resolve to human-readable documentation when called from a web browser.

Each github repository contains the ontology file (.ttl), its inferred version (the .ttl file generated on running a reasoner on the original ontology file) along with a docs and a context folder. The docs folder contains scripts for auto generation of documentation as well as the context .json file.

Finally, the ontologies can be extended to include additional process parameters if required, and a new ontology can be released with an updated version number.

2.2 Example usage

The following example is provided to demonstrate one possibility for how the application ontologies can be applied. We show a small snippet of the ontology terms applied to synthetic data from one of the partners in the json-ld format. To see the full dataset expressed through ontology concepts, please refer to the annexes. The json-ld file contains a 'context' and a 'graph' portion. The context part maps the human readable labels to the IRIs in the ontology. The graph portion contains the actual data from the dataset mapped to ontology IRIs. Please refer to the context folder in the individual GitHub repositories for the full list of terms in the context.

```
{
  "@context": "https://w3id.org/tekniker/ontology/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id":
      "https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#5dc00395_e928_46ec_9c4f_122d382eac59",
      "@type": "TreatPos",
      "hasMeasurementUnit": {
        "@id": "emmo:MilliMetre"
      },
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@id":
        "https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#09e891e9_0a90_434c_867f_e3e10311092b",
        "@type": "Real",
        "hasNumericalValue": 45.0
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

4. Dataspace integration

The application ontology is a core element in the development of the BATMACHINE dataspace. As illustrated in Figure 3, a knowledge graph will be built to document the data collected from the equipment. The measurements and machine parameters will be represented as individuals of specific concepts defined in the application ontologies.

These individuals are related to table identifiers in the time series database or objects in the object store.

Figure 3. Schematic view of the dataspace components.

The API built to interact with the dataspace will rely on this abstract representation (through the semantic concepts) to query the data using SPARQL. The machine specific concepts are connected to domain ontologies (or top-level ontology) that will enable finding correspondence and therefore connect the real data in the data sources. Working on the concept enables a more precise definition and robustness than syntactic use of the variables names as stored in the time series. The use of the ontologies will be described in more detail in the deliverable D4.2 (Data space and deployment kit (including synthetic data and documentation of the architecture and technical solution) in relation to the architecture and in deliverable D4.6 (Interfaces for software) for the exploitation of the data by external software.

5. Summary

This report encapsulates the development and deployment of application ontologies (.ttl files) tailored for the effective management of data originating from battery manufacturing equipment. The primary objective of these ontologies is to streamline structured and semantic data management techniques, particularly focusing on the diverse datasets derived from measurements and machinery. By establishing standardized frameworks for data organization and integration, these ontologies promote interoperability and enable advanced analytics.

Key suppliers in the battery manufacturing sector, including FOM, SKZ, TEKNIKER, NETZSCH, and POMECA have been engaged in the development of these application ontologies. Each ontology is meticulously structured to empower suppliers with control over their respective domains, with provisions for differentiating between public and private dissemination levels. This segregation is achieved through distinct repositories under the BATMACHINE organization, with Persistent Uniform Resource Locators (PURLs) established for long-term resource control via w3id.org.

Under the leadership of SINTEF Industry, this collaborative initiative has harnessed the collective expertise of relevant partners to develop and distribute ontologies. By adopting these application ontologies, battery manufacturing equipment suppliers can effectively manage data complexities, gain actionable insights, and improve operational efficiency. This summary highlights the crucial role of structured and semantic data management practices in fostering innovation and competitiveness within the battery manufacturing industry.

6. Deviations

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as scheduled.

7. Annexes

```
{
  "@context": "https://w3id.org/tekniker/ontology/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
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      "https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#1f5aabe9_8c23_4ff8_b563_4f723dea9192",
      "@type": "LinSpeed",
      "hasMeasurementUnit": {
        "@id": "emmo:MilliMetrePerMinute"
      },
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@id":
      "https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#f2b29f5f_0d83_49ed_963d_be07ca5a6f59 ",
        "@type": "Real",
        "hasNumericalValue": 40.0
      }
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    {
      "@id":
      "https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#5bc289ce_8033_4dd7_b856_f6aaeb38da5f",
      "@type": "HeadPos",
```

```
      "hasMeasurementUnit": {
        "@id": "emmo:MilliMetre"
      },
      "hasNumericalPart": {
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"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#facd8e75_0b45_4fbe_82bb_f4554f433894",
        "@type": "Real",
        "hasNumericalValue": 10.0
      }
    },
    {
      "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#fad144c0_9d95_442e_b79e_0a255dd8d812",
      "@type": "SyrFlow",
      "hasMeasurementUnit": {
        "@id": "emmo:MilliLitrePerHour"
      },
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#dff19b76_5700_4714_92ff_671aa7fce012",
        "@type": "Real",
        "hasNumericalValue": 40.2
      }
    },
    {
      "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#9b653ac9_4a80_4a81_8f5b_07662ed04ee7",
      "@type": "IniPos",
      "hasMeasurementUnit": {
        "@id": "emmo:MilliMetre"
      },
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#901f513d_745f_4667_a9ed_909bd5a72d68",
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        "hasNumericalValue": 5.0
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      "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#58a87229_ede8_4fe8_8728_729e91d172ff",
      "@type": "FinPos",
      "hasMeasurementUnit": {
        "@id": "emmo:MilliMetre"
      },
      "hasNumericalPart": {
```

```
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"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#458393ae_8420_47a8_b726_9f4def0bd4f0",
      "@type": "Real",
      "hasNumericalValue": 89.0
    }
  },
  {
    "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#5dc00395_e928_46ec_9c4f_122d382eac59",
    "@type": "TreatPos",
    "hasMeasurementUnit": {
      "@id": "emmo:MilliMetre"
    },
    "hasNumericalPart": {
      "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#09e891e9_0a90_434c_867f_e3e10311092b",
      "@type": "Real",
      "hasNumericalValue": 45.0
    }
  },
  {
    "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#8df7428b_f5dd_4a85_83dc_a5a449784ede",
    "@type": "Vaccum",
    "hasNumericalPart": {
      "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#4d49cd1b_2337_4aa3_be2f_f652c7a31347",
      "@type": "Boolean",
      "hasNumericalValue": true
    }
  },
  {
    "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#91bc3a6a_d6f8_422e_9f42_2981446300b1",
    "@type": "WaitTime",
    "hasMeasurementUnit": {
      "@id": "emmo:Second"
    },
    "hasNumericalPart": {
      "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#8dd82b3d_3803_4219_80f8_4a2b875e1109",
      "@type": "Real",
      "hasNumericalValue": 5.0
    }
  },
  {
```

```
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"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#de2c4bcd_9d2b_4e32_802a_effccfa6ac21",
      "@type": "Tension",
      "hasMeasurementUnit": {
        "@id": "emmo:Newton"
      },
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#2ddf48d0_f2e0_4a60_a134_f59851231a9e",
        "@type": "Real",
        "hasNumericalValue": 55.0
      }
    },
    {
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"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#03c56d86_3162_4495_b369_d9232f9c0acd",
      "@type": "MaxTime",
      "hasMeasurementUnit": {
        "@id": "emmo:Second"
      },
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#d775f525_5e16_4818_afc9_93ef9aeced2d4",
        "@type": "Real",
        "hasNumericalValue": 20.0
      }
    },
    {
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      "@type": "Switch",
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        "@id": "emmo:Second"
      },
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#f06c0987_a4fe_4594_8805_0b590bad0fe6",
        "@type": "Real",
        "hasNumericalValue": 11.0
      }
    },
    {
      "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#13d994f8_fc56_4125_81ea_458860b90871",
      "@type": "Shim",
      "hasMeasurementUnit": {
```

```
      "@id": "emmo:MilliMetre"
    },
    "hasNumericalPart": {
      "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#2f1766fd_2eae_46c0_8840_3a693e34ed13",
      "@type": "Real",
      "hasNumericalValue": 2.0
    }
  },
  {
    "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#d7d0ee3a_d0b4_4b3a_8f37_8b42a2538b52",
    "@type": "Gap",
    "hasMeasurementUnit": {
      "@id": "emmo:MilliMetre"
    },
    "hasNumericalPart": {
      "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#66194637_bee8_4a4c_b302_09f1e9caff4a",
      "@type": "Real",
      "hasNumericalValue": 11.8
    }
  },
  {
    "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#7657c110_3a8c_4ccf_8ed5_a71d5944c9fb",
    "@type": "CoatArea",
    "hasMeasurementUnit": {
      "@id": "emmo:SquareCentiMetre"
    },
    "hasNumericalPart": {
      "@id":
"https://w3id.org/tekniker/public/ontology#32b77f73_b692_4b39_b08f_ef236de00571",
      "@type": "Real",
      "hasNumericalValue": 30.8
    }
  }
]
}
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